

NIH RADx Data Hub announces major functionality and design upgrades | 05/20/2024

The National Institutes of Health (NIH) Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics Data Hub (RADx® Data Hub) announces today major functionality and design upgrades to its cloud-enabled platform. These upgrades will provide researchers more dynamic access to explore data from over 150 studies from RADx Radical, RADx-Underserved Populations, RADx-Tech, and RADx Digital Health Technologies programs. Researchers will also be gaining access to an even more robust analytics platform with tools such as Jupyter notebooks, R, Python, and SAS Viya.

The RADx Data Hub, which makes accessible datasets collected by RADx investigators, is a key component of [the NIH RADx Initiative](#). Since the Data Hub's initial launch in December 2022, it has supported secondary use of the de-identified, curated, and harmonized COVID-19 datasets within the system. The RADx Data Hub also equips researchers with the tools to analyze disparities in infection and mortality rates among different communities and in different settings.

Important new capabilities associated with this upgrade include:

- Researchers will now be able to perform study search and discover study overviews without having to create an account or log in.
- Researchers can now view extensive and informative metadata for further research planning.
- Researchers can request access to advanced analytical tools such as Data Wrangler and SAS Viya.
- For researchers who do wish to work in the cloud, access to the analytics workbench has been streamlined.
- Researchers are supported with a more intuitive user interface and extensive documentation organized for different audiences.
- Researchers can download approved data without creating a cloud-based workbench

The RADx Data Hub represents one of the largest collections of NIH COVID data available to researchers, and this upgrade introduces powerful new features that will support those wishing to conduct secondary data analyses, forge new collaborations, and build a community to accelerate scientific research and innovations.

Interested in accessing the RADx Data Hub and our community? The resources below can help you get started today:

- [Join the Community](#) to stay in touch.
- Explore the [new RADx Data Hub](#) by following along with our [Getting Started Playlist](#).
- [Read our handout](#) on receiving approval for data access.
- Are you part of a group that is interested in a demo of the new search and analysis features? Reach out to the RADx Data Hub Partners to [schedule a presentation](#).
- [Register for our June 25 webinar](#), where a panel of researchers will highlight information about data accessible via the RADx Data Hub.